

Strategies and Challenges of Organizing Learning During and After the Covid Pandemic

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Abstract

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This study aims to discover procedures for preventing the transmission of Covid-19 among the academic community. It also aims to review the Standard Operating Procedures for onsite learning and its challenges in the learning process. This study was conducted at Sam Ratulangi University, Manado- Indonesia. The type of this study is Juridical Sociology. As a result, it is found that the community has its system to prevent the transmission of Covid-19. Moreover, the strategy for dealing with challenges in the onsite learning process at Sam Ratulangi University is through a hybrid learning model. It is also called blended learning. This study's results are hoped to be an example for other universities worldwide.

1. Introduction

WHO officially declared the coronavirus (COVID-19) as a pandemic after the coronavirus spread widely world wide. It impacts the world of education and hampers the teaching and learning process. The world of education seemed to have collapsed when many teaching staff and students died because of COVID-19 (Suherman, 2021).

Education is the main sector in the development of the Indonesian nation. Quality human resources strongly support quality development (Nirmala et al., 2022). Moreover, Yuliana et al. (2022) stated that education is the key to the growth and development of quality human resources intact. To avoid the transmission and spread of the Covid19 pandemic, onsite learning has been

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changed to Online Learning. Implementation of online Learning makes all parties help and support each other in the teaching-learning process to avoid the spread of the Covid 19 Pandemic.

As time goes by, the conditions of the Covid 19 Pandemic are recovering in various sectors and leading to a *New Normal life*. Especially with the Vaccination Program from the Government, which is followed up by Higher Education Leaders in collaboration with the Health Service to vaccinate Teaching Staff, Education Personnel, and their Families and Students. The Vaccination Program restored the destruction of the world of education that was hit by the Covid 19 Pandemic.

Related to the actual conditions regarding the Covid-19 pandemic and recovery in various sectors, especially in the field of education, referring to the Joint Decree of the Four Ministers Number 01/KB/2020 dated June 15, 2020, concerning *Guidelines for Organizing Learning* in the 2020/2021 Academic Year and 2020/2021 Academic Year during the Corona Virus Disease (Covid-19) Pandemic; The Directorate General of Higher Education issues Guidelines for Organizing 2020/2021 Odd Semester Learning in Higher Education, Second Edition. This guide is a general reference and can be developed according to the needs and developments in the Covid-19 pandemic case. The Directorate General of Higher Education also coordinates with the Ministry of Research and Technology/National Research and Innovation Agency in the preparation of this guidebook, particularly in the section on the Protocol of Research Activities and Community Service for Lecturers and Students in Higher Education (Cf. Asyary, A., & Veruswati, 2020)

In order to achieve the goal of creating a quality teaching and learning system, this research not only examines the Joint Decree of the Four Ministers Number 01/KB/2020 dated June 15, 2020, but research will also examine several regulations in depth, namely: Director's Circular General Directorate General of Higher Education, Research and Technology Number 4 of 2021 Concerning Implementation of Onsite Learning for the 2021/2022 Academic Year; Regulation of the Chancellor of Sam Ratulangi University Number 1 of 2019 Concerning Guidelines for Academic Administration at Sam Ratulangi University; and the Decree of the Chancellor of Sam Ratulangi University Number 1975/UN.12/PP/2021 concerning the Academic Calendar of Sam Ratulangi University for the Genab Semester 2021/2022.

Legal norms crystallized into laws and regulations have legal goals that make their people happy so that they can present legal products that contain social justice/substantial justice values (Cf. Ardani & Ibrahim, 2022). Legislation is interpreted as written regulations that generally contain binding legal norms and are formed or determined by state institutions or authorized officials through procedures stipulated in statutory regulations. Based on Indonesian Law Number 10 of 2004 concerning the Formation of Legislation, the meaning of laws and regulations are written regulations formed by state institutions or authorized officials and are generally binding, as for the elements (Arifin, 2021).

- a. Written rules are not the same as written rules. Jurisprudence, for example, is not a written rule, even though its physical form is written. Written regulations contain the following characteristics:
 - 1) Based on Law Number 10 of 2004 concerning the Formation of Legislation, all regulations are contained in Article 7 paragraph (1) regarding the type and hierarchy of legislation, namely the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, Government Laws/Regulations Substitute Laws, Government Regulations, Presidential Regulations, and Regional Regulations;
 - 2) The regulation is established by an authorized state institution/state official;
 - 3) Making regulations through certain procedures;
 - 4) If one looks closely, both the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, Government Laws/Regulations instead of Laws, Government Regulations, and Presidential Regulations are

placed in state gazettes, and Regional Regulations are placed in regional gazettes. Thus, the regulation is placed in the official gazette.

- b. Established by State Institutions or State Officials State agencies or state officials form laws and regulations. Besides being formed by state institutions or state officials, laws and regulations can also contain sanctions for violators, which state instruments can enforce. Thus, compliance with laws and regulations comes from outside, forced by sanctions. Meanwhile, adherence to religious norms comes from within, namely self-awareness to obey them. The definition of statutory regulations in the PPP Law (Kurniawan et al., 2021) is formulated completely, contains binding legal norms, and is integrated with the planning system and procedures for forming statutory regulations.

Through various strategies and implementation efforts concerning existing health protocols, it is hoped that the conditions of the Covid-19 pandemic can be overcome and the education process can gradually return to normal. The objectives of this research are (1) to discover procedures for preventing the transmission of Covid-19 among the academic community, and (2) to review the Standard Operating Procedures for onsite learning and its challenges in the learning process. This study was conducted at Sam Ratulangi University, Manado- Indonesia

2. Materials and Methods

Research Type

As for the type of research, this is Juridical Sociology. The researchers apply the Juridical Sociological research type, a combination of Juridical and Sociological Research because the researchers try to describe the Effectiveness (Cf. Foucault, 1996) of the Regulations that exist in a group of people who are members of an institution, namely Sam Ratulangi University.

This study also uses a descriptive method that examines the status of human groups, an object, a condition, a system of thought, or an event in the present. Descriptive research aims to provide a systematic, factual, and accurate description of the facts, characteristics, and relationships between the phenomena studied. This research was carried out at Sam Ratulangi University and several locations in North Sulawesi because researchers wanted to collect data on lecturers and students about the challenges faced by students in the onsite learning system during the 2019 Corona Virus Disease pandemic.

Data Types and Sources

Sources of data needed in this study are primary data, questionnaires to respondents, interviews with sources, and secondary data through literature in the form of books, journals, laws and regulations, and seminar results.

Population and Research Sample

The population in this study are lecturers as educators, students, and Education Personnel. Data collection is conducted in several ways, including, (1) interview, namely data collection by interviewing directly in the form of unstructured question and answer with respondents who are positioned as key informants who are seen as having knowledge, understanding, and experience. (2) Questionnaires that is data collection methods by giving questionnaires or structured questions to

the respondents. (3) Documentation studies or literature studies, namely data collection, are carried out by studying journals, reports, and various written documentation or manuscripts that have links to the law and various information related to the object of this research.

Data analysis

It was then processed and analyzed through qualitative analysis. This analysis was carried out using a theoretical basis as an analytical knife in explaining the phenomenon that became this study.

3. Results and Discussions

Procedures for preventing the transmission of Covid-19 among the academic community of Sam Ratulangi University

COVID-19 pandemics the spreading of Coronavirus disease around the world. A coronavirus new type named SARS-CoV-2 Plague COVID-19 causes this disease was first detected in Wuhan, China, on December 1, 2019, and designated as pandemic by World Health Organization (WHO) on March 11, 2020 (Schub, 2020). WHO (World Health Organization) officially declared the coronavirus (COVID-19) a pandemic on March 9, 2020.

The coronavirus has spread widely in the world. A pandemic sounds scary, but actually, it has nothing to do with the malignancy of the disease but rather with its widespread spread. The coronavirus generally causes mild or moderate symptoms, such as fever and cough, and most can recover within a few weeks. But for some people at high risk (elderly groups and people with chronic health problems, such as heart disease, high blood pressure, or diabetes), the coronavirus can cause serious health problems. Most victims come from that risk group. That's why we all need to understand how to reduce risk, keep abreast of information and know what to do when experiencing symptoms. Based on research result, the procedures for preventing the transmission of Covid-19 among the academic community at Sam Ratulangi University, namely:

- a. In collaboration with RSU, Prof. dr. Kandou created the Covid 19 Vaccine Laboratory
- b. Holding Covid 19 Vaccination in stages for all Unsrat Leaders
- c. Holding Covid 19 Vaccination in stages for all Lecturers (Educators)
- d. Holding Covid 19 Vaccination in stages for all Employees (Educational Personnel)
- e. Holding Covid 19 Vaccination in stages for all Sam Ratulangi University Students.
- f. Collaborating with the Manado City Government to Hold Covid 19 Vaccinations for Communities who need the Covid 19 Vaccine
- g. Organizing Covid 19 Vaccination for the Elderly Community
- h. In the framework of the Onsite Program, Booster Vaccinations are held in stages for all Lecturers (Educators) and Employees (Educational Staff)
- i. In the framework of the Onsite Program, booster vaccinations are held in stages for all students.
- j. Making Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) during the Covid-19 Pandemic.
- k. Making Health Protocol Regulations during the Covid-19 Pandemic.

Standard Operational Procedures for Onsite Learning at Sam Ratulangi University

Onsite learning is a conventional learning model that seeks to convey knowledge to students by bringing teachers and students together in a room for Learning with planned characteristics, place-based orientation, and social interaction (Manullang et al., 2022).

For strategic stages of competency achievement, learning activities need to be designed and implemented effectively and efficiently to obtain maximum results. Based on learning activities consisting of onsite, structured, and unstructured independent activities. This direct learning is designed to be able to monitor events/changes that occur in students with onsite learning. Onsite learning is a good learning method because, with onsite learning, a close social relationship is established between students and lecturers, as well as students and students themselves through the interaction process created in the learning process (Cf. Arafah et al., 2022).

Concerning Onsite Learning, is issued circular Letter 4 of 2021 Concerning the Implementation of Onsite Learning for the 2021/2022 Academic Year. In implementing learning, tertiary institutions must prioritize the health and safety of campus residents (students, lecturers, and education staff) and the surrounding community. If onsite learning will be held, both lectures, practicums. For preparation, the university has its strategy as follows.

- 1) Universities can carry out preparations for implementing onsite learning according to the level of implementation of restrictions on community activities (PPKM) according to the Instruction of the Minister of Home Affairs regarding the implementation of restrictions on community activities. Universities in the PPKM areas level 1, level 2, and level 3 can hold limited onsite learning and report to the local regional task force. In addition to reporting to the regional task force, private tertiary institutions also report to the Higher Education Service Institution.
- 2) Higher education can only organize curricular activities through learning, research, and community service.
- 3) Universities are ready to implement the health protocol stipulated in the Joint Decree above and Decree of the Minister of Health Number HK.01.07/MENKES/413/2020 concerning Guidelines for the Prevention and Control of Coronavirus Disease 2019 (Covid-19).
- 4) Universities have formed a task force for handling Covid-19 in tertiary institutions to compile and implement standard operating procedures for health protocols.
- 5) Higher education leaders issue learning guidelines, graduations, and other activities for academics and education staff within the higher education environment.
- 6) There are no objections from parents/guardians to students participating in onsite learning.

For the implementation stages, the strategy is stated as follows.

- 1) Report on the implementation of learning to the Covid-19 handling task force regularly.
- 2) Perform testing and tracing regularly.
- 3) Academics and academic staff who carry out activities on campus must:
 - a) Students and lecturers should be in good health condition;
 - b) Students and lecturers should already got the vaccination. For those who have not been vaccinated, make a statement containing information that the person concerned has not received a vaccination quota or cannot be vaccinated for certain reasons (has comorbidities);
 - c) Students and lecturers should obtain parental consent, as evidenced by a statement;
 - d) For students who are not willing to do onsite learning, they can choose online learning;
 - e) Students from outside the region/overseas are required to ensure that they are in good health, carry out independent quarantine for 14 days or carry out a swab test, or according to regulations/protocols that apply in the local area;

- 4). Having action to prevent the spread of Covid-19 by:
 - a) disinfecting infrastructure facilities in the higher education environment before and after learning focused on the facilities used during onsite learning;
 - b) carry out body temperature checks for everyone who enters college;
 - c) avoid using closed learning facilities, causing crowds, and close contact;
 - d) provide hand washing/hand sanitizer in strategic places;
 - e) using 3 (three) layers of cloth masks or disposable masks\surgical masks that cover the nose and mouth;
 - f) apply a minimum distance of 1.5 (one point five) meters between people;
 - g) limit the use of space to a maximum of 50% (fifty percent) of the room/class/laboratory occupancy capacity and a maximum of 25 (twenty-five) people;
 - h) implementing mutual caring, caring, and protecting efforts;
 - i) apply proper coughing/sneezing ethics;
 - j) provide temporary isolation rooms for academics and education staff who have symptoms/criteria for Covid-19;
 - k) prepare a mechanism for handling findings of Covid-19 cases in tertiary institutions (both for those concerned and contact tracing);
 - l) prepare support for emergency measures to handle Covid-19; And
 - m) report to the local, regional Covid-19 handling task force unit if a Covid-19 case is found.
- 5) Campus residents are expected to become ambassadors for behavior change in their respective environments.
- 6) If positive confirmed cases of Covid-19 are found in tertiary institutions, the higher education leaders temporarily stop onsite learning in confirmed positive areas for Covid-19 until conditions are safe.
- 7) In the event of an increase in the status of an increase in the risk of Covid-19 in the district/city, the head of the tertiary institution will coordinate with the local Covid-19 handling task force to continue or stop onsite learning.

Next, for monitoring stage, the university has its strategy as follows.

- 1) Universities enforce standard operating procedures for health protocols and regularly monitor and evaluate the implementation of standard operating procedures for enforcing health protocols.
- 2) Universities are expected to be able to share experiences and good practices in implementing blended learning during the Covid-19 pandemic.
- 3) Higher Education Service Institutions regularly monitor onsite learning activities in tertiary institutions, and monitoring results can be used as recommendations for follow-up of onsite learning activities.

This circular letter is submitted for attention and is implemented accordingly (Directorate General of Higher Education, 2021).

Moreover, the Standard Operational Procedures for Face to Face/Offline Learning at Sam Ratulangi University, namely:

a. Provision:

- 1) Students are college participants are registered and active students in the current semester.
- 2) Students have filled out the KRS and have received approval from the Academic Advisor.
- 3) Lectures run if the number, of course, participants is at least three people, and if the number of students is less than three people, then learning activities are carried out in the form of tutorials.
- 4) Subject lecturers, together with study program managers, make adjustments to Course Learning Outcomes (CPMK) and RPKPS to be able to adjust to the learning method to be used (online method or a combination of online and offline methods).

The procedures are as follows.

- 1) Before the new semester started, the study program manager held a lecturer meeting to discuss the distribution of teaching assignments in the study program.
- 2) The Head of the Study Program sends a list of lecturers giving the course to the Dean, to make a Letter of Assignment for Lecturers who will teach in the current semester.
- 3) The Dean issues a Letter of Assignment to teach the course to the supporting lecturer, submitted through the study program manager.
- 4) The academic department of the study program downloads the student participant data based on the KRS that has been filled in by students and makes a list of attendees for the lecture participants.
- 5) The academic department of the study program arranges and uses lecture halls in coordination with the academic department.
- 6) The academic department of the study program announces class schedules to students and lecturers in charge of the course.
- 7) The academic department of the study program is responsible for the readiness of facilities and equipment for holding lectures, including:
 - a) We provide and ensure that lecture equipment functions properly.
 - b) Measure and coordinate with the equipment department that the lecture halls and equipment in the classroom are cleaned regularly using germ-killing fluids (des infections).
 - c) Arrange chairs in the lecture hall, so they are at least 1 meter apart, according to the Covid 19 protocol.
 - d) Ensure the availability of stationery, hand sanitizers, microphone protective covers, tissues, and indoor cooling fans in each classroom.

b. Lecture implementation

- 1) Students download the Unsrat Inspire Portal application on their respective mobile devices to be used as a medium for recording attendance for each lecture.
- 2) Students attend class before lectures begin, then make attendance through the Unsrat Inspire Portal application.
- 3) Students /lecturers who have a fever (body temperature above 37.5oC) or are sick are not allowed to attend lectures.
- 4) During lecture activities, students and lecturers must wear masks, or masks plus face shields.

- 5) In each form of teaching and learning activity, student seats are arranged so that the distance between students or lecturers is a minimum of 1 meter.
- 6) do not shake hands or make physical contact between lecture Participants/lecturers.
- 7) The microphone is only held and used by the lecturer. The use of alternate microphones is not allowed.
- 8) Students /lecturers bring and use their stationery. Avoid using items/stationery interchangeably or borrowing from each other.
- 9) The lecture length, try to have a fresh air flow. Windows must be opened, the use of indoor air conditioners is avoided, and if necessary, use fans to cool the room.

Strategies for dealing with Challenges in the Onsite Learning Process at Sam Ratulangi University

Strategy is a fundamental pattern of goals and planning, distribution of resources, and organizational interactions with markets, competitors, and environmental factors (Setiadi et al., 2020). Strategy can be interpreted as a plan to distribute and use military and material forces in certain areas to achieve certain action goals (CK et al, 2022). Strategy is a unified, broad, and integrated plan that links the company's strategic advantages with environmental challenges, designed to ensure that the main goals of the company can be achieved through proper implementation by the organization.

A strategy involves several integrated and coordinated actions to utilize core competencies and gain a competitive advantage. A company's success, as measured by strategic competitiveness and high profitability, is a function of the company's ability to develop and use new core competencies faster than competitors' efforts to imitate existing advantages. So, the strategy is a plan to achieve the desired goal (Cf. Partawa et al., 2022).

Based on the research results of the hybrid learning model applied during the Covid-19 pandemic, it can be used as material for future policymaking. Whether we admit it or not, even though we hope that the Covid-19 pandemic will end soon, education, technology, and science will continue to develop and require humans to use them by following these developments wisely.

The learning model is a conceptual framework that describes systematic procedures for organizing learning experiences to achieve certain Learning goals and serves as a guide for learning designers and teachers in planning and implementing learning activities. The learning model chosen must be appropriate and adapted to the conditions.

Hybrid Learning can also be called blended learning. Blended learning is a model that combines onsite Learning and Online Learning. The hybrid learning model is a model that combines innovation and technological advances in online learning with interaction and participation from conventional or onsite learning models. Then various models of learning from home emerged other than online, namely offline or off-network and bolster or itinerant teachers.

Online is a learning model carried out remotely using media from the internet and other supporting tools such as cell phones and computers. This learning model is also called a technology-based learning model. Learning is different from usual because it emphasizes the thoroughness and foresight of students to receive and process information presented online (Ghaemi, H., & Ataei, 2022).

The online learning model has advantages, such as overcoming distance and time problems, building a new learning atmosphere, and fostering students' enthusiasm for learning. The offline learning model is learning that does not use a computer network. Types of offline activities include watching television shows as learning materials or doing assignments to do work with the guidance

of parents at home. Offline can also be in the form of onsite learning at school by applying certain rules.

4. Conclusion

Procedures for preventing the transmission of Covid-19 among the academic community of Sam Ratulangi University, in the form of a). Collaboration with RSU Prof. dr. Kandou created the Covid-19 Vaccine Laboratory; b). Holding Covid 19 Vaccination in stages for all Unsrat Leaders, Lecturers (Educators), Staff (Educational Staff), AndSam Ratulangi University students; c). Collaborating with the Manado City Government to Hold Covid 19 Vaccinations for Communities who need a Covid 19 Vaccine; d). Organizing Covid 19 Vaccination for the (Elderly Community; e). In the framework of the Onsite Program, Booster Vaccinations are held in stages for all Lecturers (Educators) and Employees (Educational Staff); f) In the framework of the Onsite Program, booster vaccinations are held in stages for all students; g). Creating Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) during the Covid-19 (Pandemic; h). Making Health Protocol Regulations during the Covid-19 Pandemic.

Standard Operational Procedures for Onsite Learning at Sam Ratulangi University, in the form of a) Lecture room, b). Implementation of Lectures; c). Monitoring. Next, the hybrid learning model, called blended learning, is the strategy for dealing with challenges in the onsite learning process at Sam Ratulangi University. This model combines onsite Learning and Online Learning.

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